

IS EU'S WIND POWER FLEET GREEN FOR ALL? EXPLORING REGIONALISED SOCIO-ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS

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ABSTRACT

Despite being a renewable energy source, wind power is not exempt of environmental impacts. These impacts are not limited to those on the site of operation but also include those related to all the activities across the supply chain. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of wind turbines analyse accumulated impacts from the raw material extraction to the decommissioning of power plants. However, wind turbine LCA studies yield spatially aggregated results, without a distinction of which part of the impacts take place where.

To address this gap, we introduce in this paper a method to distinguish between operational site (onsite) and supply chain (offsite) impacts in energy technologies. This differentiation was applied to wind inventories of different capacities and compared to photovoltaics and coal power plants for reference. Results show a dominance of offsite impacts in renewable energy infrastructures except for Land Occupation. Also, an analysis of the Land Occupation impacts of the European wind turbine fleet was carried out, highlighting that lower populated areas receive the biggest portion of the impacts.

INTRODUCTION

The Energy Union Strategy (European Commission, 2015) calls for a decarbonisation of the energy system of Member States that contributes to the 2050 carbon neutrality scenario set by the 2030 Climate Target Plan (European Commission, 2020). Part of the decarbonisation strategy is the promotion of wind energy, which has been slowly increasing its share in the European electricity mix in recent years. Wind energy represented 17% of the mix (254 GW) in year 2022, and the EU aims to achieve 510 GW of wind power installed capacity by 2030, which supposes to double the current capacity within eight years (WindEurope, 2023).

As it relies in a renewable resource, wind power does not emit greenhouse gases (GHG) on the operation site. However, other life-cycle stages with associated GHG emissions, namely: the raw materials extraction, manufacturing, transportation or decommissioning of the wind turbines. Moreover, beyond contribution to climate change wind power does have other environmental impacts, such as land use change or water consumption. In order to understand the trade-offs between the different impacts some authors call for a holistic picture of the environmental implications of wind energy production (Hauschild et al., 2018). Life cycle assessment (LCA) has been widely used with this purpose, analysing the environmental impacts of onshore (Bonou et al., 2016; Chipindula et al., 2018; Mendecka & Lombardi, 2019; Sacchi et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2018) and offshore turbines (Bang et al., 2019; Brussa et al., 2023; Li et al., 2022; Poujol et al., 2020; Raadal et al., 2014; Tsai et al., 2016) in a wide range of power capacities ranging from 100 kW to 8 MW. However, most of the studies calculate aggregated impacts for the full value chain, without separating impacts at the location where the turbine is operating from the rest. Because the wind industry has a complex globalised value chain, this separation would not only provide a better understanding of the impacts that are burdened over the nearby populations, but also the global geographical distribution of the environmental impacts. Although there are already a few applications in the energy sector (C. L. Mutel et al., 2012; C. L. Mutel & Hellweg, 2009), its focus on wind energy has not been explored yet.

A regionalised LCA (Potting & Hauschild, 2006) requires georeferenced inventory data and regionalised Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) methods (C. Mutel et al., 2019), both still in early development stages. In this work, a methodology to regionalise wind power inventory data was developed and then applied in a screening of the regional distribution of processes and environmental impacts associated to wind energy. This method allows to distinguish those processes and impacts across the entire life cycle that occur where the wind power infrastructure is located (*onsite* from now on) from the processes and impacts happening elsewhere along the value chain (i.e., *offsite*). It is a novel approach to inventory regionalisation that disaggregates with detail all the onsite flows from a power infrastructure.

The method was applied to wind turbine inventories from the commercial LCA database Ecoinvent v3.9.1 (Wernet et al., 2016) (onshore: 800 kW, 2 MW, 4.5 MW, and offshore: 2 MW), distinguishing impacts per MW of infrastructure and per kWh of electricity produced. The results were compared to two other renewable technology inventories (photovoltaics open ground and rooftop) and a non-renewable technology (coal 500 MW). Finally, the method was used to calculate the impacts of current EU wind fleet, as a first step into a comprehensive study of the entire European electricity system.

METHODS

Even though electricity-related inventories in life-cycle databases such as Ecoinvent provide spatial information, this is not specific enough to distinguish onsite from offsite activities and impacts. In fact, while the geographical reference of electricity production data in Ecoinvent is presented by country or region, power infrastructure inventories tend to be assigned to a general geography called “Rest of the World”. However, in reality, power infrastructure is very specifically located in the territory and that specific location is key to properly assess the distribution of environmental impacts.

This work explores the background of wind turbine inventories, searching for and selecting those processes that happen onsite. These include excavation activities to set the infrastructure, the diesel burned by machinery during installation, operation, maintenance or dismantling activities, auxiliary roads constructed to access the infrastructure, or emissions during the collection for final disposal once the infrastructure reaches the end-of-life, as well as the infrastructure inventories themselves.

The software Brightway 2.5 (Mutel, 2017) was used to disaggregate wind energy inventories from Ecoinvent into onsite and offsite activities. Wind turbine inventories and electricity production inventories with a common geography (“Rest of the world” and Spain, respectively) were used to ensure the comparability of results. An LCIA of the onsite impacts was carried out. Two functional units were defined: the deployment of 1 MW of capacity infrastructure and the generation of 1 kWh (i.e., infrastructure and use). The spatially disaggregated inventories were used to get the onsite impacts, and unmodified Ecoinvent 3.9.1 inventories were used to calculate total impacts (i.e., onsite plus offsite). We selected eight indicators from the LCIA method ReCiPe 2016 v1.1 midpoint (H) (Huijbregts et al., 2017): Global Warming (GW), Land Occupation (LO), Particulate Matter Formation (PMF), Water Consumption (WC), Surplus Ore (SO) and Fossil Fuel (FF).

Then, an analysis of onsite/offsite impacts of the current European wind fleet power capacity was carried out. Data on the location and technical parameters of the European wind farms was purchased from thewindpower.net. Offshore, planned and under construction wind parks were left out of the analysis. An LCA with both the onsite and unmodified Ecoinvent inventories (800 kW, 2 MW and 4.5 MW inventories) was performed for each park, upscaling the inventories to the power capacity of the park. Turbines equal or smaller than 1 MW were assigned the 800 kW inventory, while turbines between 1 MW and 3 MW were assigned the 2 MW inventory and turbines bigger than 3 MW were assigned the 4.5 MW. Then, the results were geographically aggregated into NUTS-3 regions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Impacts per MW

Figure 1a shows the share of onsite from the total impacts of deploying 1 MW of wind power infrastructure per capacity and a comparison for reference with other energy technologies. Onsite impact is below 10% for all technologies for all indicators except Land Occupation. This means that raw material extraction, processing and manufacture activities happening offsite contribute more to the total life cycle impacts than installation, maintenance, or dismantling onsite operations for all technologies. This result implies that the

electrification and impulse of renewable energy that accompanies the energy transition shifts onsite impacts to offsite locations, except for the occupation of land.

Onsite Land Occupation has not only the highest share but also a wide range that goes from 0 to 92%. On the lower side are rooftop photovoltaics and wind offshore, which do not entail any land use change, leading to null LO impacts. In the first case, that is because they are installed in already anthropized spaces, while in the second case they occupy the seabed, which is not considered in the LO impact indicator chosen. On the upper side are open ground photovoltaics (with 92% of onsite LO impact) and small wind technologies of 800 kW (72%) and 2 MW (69%). These have a higher share of onsite LO than bigger wind turbines of 4.5 MW (29%) and coal (40%). The marginal increase in land use per MW as modelled in Ecoinvent is not linear and decreases with the capacity. That is, the marginal difference in LO per MW between turbines of 1 MW and 2 MW is bigger than the marginal difference between 2 MW and 3 MW. The higher share of onsite LO in smaller wind turbines with respect to higher capacity infrastructure also indicates that the land transformation and occupation in the deployment site is higher for decentralized than for centralised power plants.

Figure 1. a) Relative onsite/total impacts percentage of deploying 1 MW of infrastructure, b) onsite impacts of deploying 1 MW of infrastructure normalised to the highest onsite impact in each indicator, c) relative onsite/total impacts percentage of producing 1 kWh of electricity, and d) onsite impacts of producing 1 kWh of electricity normalised to the highest onsite impact in each indicator. For GW, LO, PMF, and WCP impact indicators, and wind onshore (800 kW – wind_on 800kW, 2MW – wind_on 2MW, 4.5MW – wind_on 4.5MW), wind offshore (wind_off 2MW), photovoltaics (open ground – pv_open, slanted rooftop – pv_roof), and coal 500MW (coal_500MW) power plants. Photovoltaic technologies are represented in dotted colours, wind technologies in striped colours, whereas coal in solid dark blue.

Regarding onsite water consumption, it is only the case for photovoltaic technologies, but it is still less than 1%. The null onsite water consumption for the rest of technologies is due to the inventory disaggregation methodology, which does not capture the onsite water use of in-situ concrete manufacturing, which is a common approach in infrastructure building.

Figure 1b shows the onsite impact per MW normalised to the highest value of each impact indicator. Thus, the technology with the highest onsite impact is assigned a 100%. Regarding GW and PMF, coal and 2 MW wind onshore turbines have the highest onsite impacts. They are followed by 4.5 MW wind turbines and wind offshore with impacts higher than 68% in GW and higher than 80% in PMF. This means that these technologies have more onsite GW and PMF impacts per MW than the 800 kW wind turbines or the solar photovoltaic panels. Photovoltaics in open ground is the costliest in terms of onsite LO by a large difference. All technologies have null WC impacts, except for the two types of photovoltaics, whose

installations consume similar amounts of water onsite. Finally, Surplus Ore and Fossil Fuel impact indicators were 100% offsite for all renewable and non-renewable technologies, and therefore not depicted in Figure 1.

Impacts per kWh

Similarly to figure 1a, figure 1c shows the share of onsite from the total impacts of producing 1 kWh of electricity with wind power infrastructure with different capacities and a comparison for reference with other energy technologies. In here, not only the material extraction, manufacturing and installation of infrastructure was considered, but also its maintenance and use. There is a broad difference between the onsite impact share of fossil-based and the share of renewable technologies. One explanation is that fossil fuel plants emit gases and pollutants to the atmosphere during the combustion (onsite) that contribute to different impact indicators. Once again, the LO of the infrastructure dominates the impacts of renewable technologies as it has a higher onsite share than in the rest of the value chain.

This is also the case for the total onsite impacts per kWh shown in figure 1d. Indeed, the onsite share of LO of coal power plants become negligible against the offsite mining processes needed to obtain coal. However, for other impact indicators, coal power plants dominate total onsite impacts, like WC (due to onsite water demands to refrigerate the reactor and dissipate heat) and GW impacts, which are four orders of magnitude higher than wind offshore, the second onsite most emitting technology.

European wind fleet

With the aim of understanding onsite/offsite impact dynamics of current power plants in Europe, we carried out an analysis of the LO of the European onshore wind fleet in 2020 using Ecoinvent inventories, as it is the indicator with more variability of onsite impacts among onshore wind technologies. As shown above, bigger turbines (4.5 MW) are up to a 65% more efficient in terms of LO per MW installed than the smallest turbines (800 kW). Figure 2 (left) shows onsite LO impact of the European wind fleet (2020) aggregated by NUTS-3 regions. This is mainly influenced by two factors: (i) the number of turbines and (ii) their power capacity distribution. Therefore, regions with large amounts of small turbines, which tend to be as well older, will have the greatest impacts. That is the case of Denmark, East Germany and North Spain, where the first impulse of small turbine installations started in 1970s, early 1990s and late 1990s, respectively. In the opposite side, for example, we would find Norway and Finland with initial wind turbine adoptions in early 2010s and bigger than 2.7 MW mean turbine size in both cases.

We compared these results with a map of the European population density (Figure 2, right) to check if there is any overlap between the concentration of LO impacts and population. For most countries, lower population density correlates with higher LO impacts, and vice versa. A clear example of this trend is Ireland, where while most people concentrate in the East (Dublin and its metropolitan area), LO impacts are the highest in the North and Western regions. These results emphasise the peripheralization of the energy transition that affects mostly local and rural communities with low political power (O'Sullivan et al., 2020).

Figure 2. Onsite LO impact of the European wind fleet (2020) in NUTS-3 regions (left), and Population density in Europe (persons/km²) in 2019 (right).

CONCLUSIONS

This work examines onsite and offsite impacts of the deployment of wind energy infrastructure and its implementation across Europe. Our results show that the energy transition will bring a shift from onsite to offsite impacts, except for Land occupation. Also, that turbines with less capacity have higher relative impacts. The current wind fleet seems to be located in less densely populated areas, displacing the impacts from the place where the electricity will finally be used and raising issues of distributive justice, a crucial issue that some authors have emphasised (Jenkins et al., 2016).

Although the main goal of the transition is to phase out fossil fuels and reduce GHG emissions of the energy system globally, other environmental impacts across the whole life cycle of energy technologies must be considered to avoid unforeseen impacts. In this regard, it is crucial to acknowledge and quantify the environmental impact shifting from the energy production site to the value chain that renewable energies entail. The method presented and applied in this paper makes steps in this direction as it provides environmental impact results with high spatial resolution for energy technologies. Thus, it does not only allow to analyse technologies in terms of impact shifting, but it also has the potential to shed light on the local impacts that communities hosting new renewable energy infrastructure must endure, which increase significantly in terms of Land Occupation. Further work should include other types of electricity production sites in Europe and a wider range of environmental impacts.

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REFERENCES

- Bang, J.-I., Ma, C., Tarantino, E., Vela, A., Yamane, D., Suh, S., Geyer, R., & Alizadeh, M. (2019). *Life Cycle Assessment of Greenhouse Gas Emissions for Floating Offshore Wind Energy in California* Committee in charge.

- Bonou, A., Laurent, A., & Olsen, S. I. (2016). Life cycle assessment of onshore and offshore wind energy—from theory to application. *Applied Energy*, *180*, 327–337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.07.058>
- Brussa, G., Grosso, M., & Rigamonti, L. (2023). Life cycle assessment of a floating offshore wind farm in Italy. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, *39*, 134–144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2023.05.006>
- Chipindula, J., Botlaguduru, V. S. V., Du, H., Kommalapati, R. R., & Huque, Z. (2018). Life cycle environmental impact of onshore and offshore wind farms in Texas. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, *10*(6). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10062022>
- European Commission. (2015). A Framework Strategy for a Resilient Energy Union with a Forward-Looking Climate Change Policy.
- European Commission. (2020). 2030 Climate Target Plan.
- Hauschild, M. Z., Rosenbaum, R. K., & Olsen, S. I. (2018). Life Cycle Assessment.
- Huijbregts, M. A. J., Steinmann, Z. J. N., Elshout, P. M. F., Stam, G., Verones, F., Vieira, M., Zijp, M., Hollander, A., & van Zelm, R. (2017). ReCiPe2016: a harmonised life cycle impact assessment method at midpoint and endpoint level. *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, *22*(2), 138–147. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1246-y>
- Jenkins, K., McCauley, D., Heffron, R., Stephan, H., & Rehner, R. (2016). Energy justice: A conceptual review. In *Energy Research and Social Science* (Vol. 11, pp. 174–182). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2015.10.004>
- Li, C., Mogollón, J. M., Tukker, A., & Steubing, B. (2022). Environmental Impacts of Global Offshore Wind Energy Development until 2040. *Environmental Science and Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.2c02183>
- Mendecka, B., & Lombardi, L. (2019). Life cycle environmental impacts of wind energy technologies: A review of simplified models and harmonization of the results. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, *111*, 462–480. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.05.019>
- Mutel, C. (2017). Brightway: An open source framework for Life Cycle Assessment. *The Journal of Open Source Software*, *2*(12), 236. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.00236>
- Mutel, C. L., & Hellweg, S. (2009). Regionalized life cycle assessment: Computational methodology and application to inventory databases. *Environmental Science and Technology*, *43*(15), 5797–5803. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es803002j>
- Mutel, C. L., Pfister, S., & Hellweg, S. (2012). GIS-based regionalized life cycle assessment: How Big is small enough? Methodology and case study of electricity generation. *Environmental Science and Technology*, *46*(2), 1096–1103. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es203117z>
- Mutel, C., Liao, X., Patouillard, L., Bare, J., Fantke, P., Frischknecht, R., Hauschild, M., Jolliet, O., Maia de Souza, D., Laurent, A., Pfister, S., & Verones, F. (2019). Overview and recommendations for regionalized life cycle impact assessment. *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, *24*(5), 856–865. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-018-1539-4>
- O’Sullivan, K., Golubchikov, O., & Mehmood, A. (2020). Uneven energy transitions: Understanding continued energy peripheralization in rural communities. *Energy Policy*, *138*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111288>
- Potting, J., & Hauschild, M. Z. (2006). Spatial differentiation in life cycle impact assessment: A decade of method development to increase the environmental realism of LCIA. In *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* (Vol. 11, Issue SPEC. ISS. 1, pp. 11–13). <https://doi.org/10.1065/lca2006.04.005>
- Poujol, B., Prieur-Vernat, A., Dubranna, J., Besseau, R., Blanc, I., & Pérez-López, P. (2020). Site-specific life cycle assessment of a pilot floating offshore wind farm based on suppliers’ data and geo-located wind data. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, *24*(1), 248–262. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12989>
- Raadal, H. L., Vold, B. I., Myhr, A., & Nygaard, T. A. (2014). GHG emissions and energy performance of offshore wind power. *Renewable Energy*, *66*, 314–324. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2013.11.075>
- Sacchi, R., Besseau, R., Pérez-López, P., & Blanc, I. (2019). Exploring technologically, temporally and geographically-sensitive life cycle inventories for wind turbines: A parameterized model for Denmark. *Renewable Energy*, *132*, 1238–1250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2018.09.020>
- Tsai, L., Kelly, J. C., Simon, B. S., Chalat, R. M., & Keoleian, G. A. (2016). Life Cycle Assessment of Offshore Wind Farm Siting: Effects of Locational Factors, Lake Depth, and Distance from Shore. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, *20*(6), 1370–1383. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12400>
- Wernet, G., Bauer, C., Steubing, B., Reinhard, J., Moreno-Ruiz, E., & Weidema, B. (2016). The ecoinvent database version 3 (part I): overview and methodology. *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, *21*(9), 1218–1230. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1087-8>
- WindEurope. (2023). Wind energy in Europe. 2022 Statistics and the outlook for 2023–2027
- Xu, L., Pang, M., Zhang, L., Poganietz, W. R., & Marathe, S. D. (2018). Life cycle assessment of onshore wind power systems in China. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, *132*, 361–368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.06.014>